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A nonlinear time transformation method to compute all the coefficients for the homoclinic bifurcation in the quadratic Takens-Bogdanov normal form

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Abstract In this paper, we present an algorithm based on the nonlinear time transformation method to approximate homoclinic orbits in planar autonomous nonlinear oscillators. With this approach, a unique perturbation solution up to any desired order can be obtained for them using trigonometric functions. To demonstrate its efficiency, the method is applied to calculate the homoclinic connection, both in the phase space and in the parameter space, of the versal unfolding of the non-degenerate Takens-Bogdanov singularity. Our approach

considerably improves the results obtained so far by other methods (Melnikov, Poincaré-Lindstedt, regular perturbations, multiple scales, ...). The approximations achieved to different orders are confirmed by numerical continuation.

Keywords Nonlinear time transformation · Takens-Bogdanov bifurcation · Melnikov function · homoclinic orbit

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1 Introduction

Homoclinic and heteroclinic orbits are of great interest in the study of nonlinear dynamical systems. They play an important role in the investigation of chaotic behavior. In order to guarantee the existence of connecting orbits, the most widely used technique is the Melnikov function, see [1,2]. Also, several perturbation methods have been developed to approximate the bifurcation in a perturbed system. For instance, the hyperbolic perturbation method [3,4] has been developed to study the homoclinic orbits in nonlinear autonomous oscillators. Belhaq et al. [5] present the elliptic Lindstedt-Poincaré (L-P) method with a collision criterion (this criterion can be extended to 3D systems [6]). Several modified L-P methods have also been developed; see for instance [7–9]. In 2011, Cao et al. [11] proposed the nonlinear time transformation (NTT) method to approximate the connecting orbits using trigonometric functions. Recently, this method was applied to predict homoclinic orbits in a 4-dimensional system [10]. However, to the best of our knowledge, in the literature there does not exist a simple procedure to obtain the approximation of the bifurcation curve as well as the connecting orbits up to very high-order.

The main purpose of this paper is to present an algorithm based on the NTT method to obtain a perturbation solution of the homoclinic orbit up to any desired order. With the higher-order solution, the accuracy of the approximation can be greatly improved for large parameter values. To illustrate its usefulness and effectiveness, we will apply this method to the well-known versal unfolding of the nondegenerate Takens-Bogdanov singularity (nondiagonalizable double-zero eigenvalue) $\dot{x} = y$,

$$\dot{y} = \eta_1 + \eta_2 y + x^2 + xy. \quad (1)$$

The dynamics of this system has been well studied [12–16] as it is very useful in the analysis of the applications where a Takens-Bogdanov bifurcation occurs (see, for instance, [17–26]). For $\eta_1 < 0$, it possesses a saddle $(\sqrt{-\eta_1}, 0)$ and a focus $(-\sqrt{-\eta_1}, 0)$. These equilibria emerge in a saddle-node bifurcation when $\eta_1 = 0$, $\eta_2 \neq 0$. The focus undergoes a Hopf bifurcation **H** if $\eta_2 = \sqrt{-\eta_1}$; see Fig. 1. By decreasing the parameter η_2 , an unstable periodic orbit arises from the Hopf bifurcation and disappears when it collides with the saddle. Consequently, a homoclinic connection **Hom** can be observed. The uniqueness of the periodic orbit is verified in [27]. Recently, Gasull et al. [28] have proved the Perko’s conjectures about some analytic properties of the homoclinic bifurcation curve. In [29], they also provide the first four terms for the approximation of the homoclinic bifurcation curve. For all we know, this is the best approximation achieved so far. However, the expression for the homoclinic orbit is not given. Al-Hdaibat et al. [30] apply the regular-perturbation (R-P) method and the generalized Lindstedt-Poincaré (L-P) method to investigate the homoclinic bifurcation. They obtain the approximations for the bifurcation curve as well as the homoclinic orbit up to the third-order (they provide the first two terms of the asymptotic expansion). Our goal is to improve the approximation by finding the higher-order perturbation solution, using the NTT method with trigonometric functions. The success of our approach is summarized in the formula (44) where, for brevity, we only show the first eleven terms of the asymptotic development, obtained in a few seconds with a standard laptop. Note that the method allows knowing to any order, with the only limitation of the hardware used.

The paper is organized as follows. In section 2, we present the NTT method and computations for finding up to any desired order the approximation for the homoclinic bifurcations. In section 3, we apply the method to the versal unfolding of the nondegenerate Takens-Bogdanov singularity. In this way, we clearly improve the previous analytical results found in the literature. Finally, some conclusions are given in section 4.

Fig. 1 Qualitative partial bifurcation set for system (1).

2 The nonlinear time transformation method

In this section, we introduce the NTT method for obtaining the approximation of the homoclinic orbits in autonomous nonlinear oscillators. The application of the NTT method to approximate the connecting orbits was first presented in [11]. The authors have shown the computation of the first and second order approximations. Here, we introduce an algorithm to obtain the perturbation solution up to any desired order.

We consider a vector field in \mathbb{R}^2 of the form

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x} &= y, \\ \dot{y} &= g(x) + \varepsilon [f(x, y) + \mu h(x, y)], \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

with smooth functions $g(x)$, $f(x, y)$ and $h(x, y)$, $\varepsilon \ll 1$ and μ are perturbation and system parameters, respectively. Assume that the unperturbed system possesses a homoclinic orbit Γ_0 to the hyperbolic saddle E_0 .

Following the notation of [11], we introduce the nonlinear time transformation $\varphi(t)$ of the form

$$\frac{d\varphi}{dt} = \Phi(\varphi), \quad \Phi(\varphi + 2\pi) = \Phi(\varphi). \quad (3)$$

If $\varphi(t) \rightarrow \varphi_{\pm}$ as $t \rightarrow \pm\infty$ for the homoclinic orbit, we have the following condition

$$\Phi(\varphi_{\pm}) = 0, \quad (4)$$

since the integration of (3) must diverge.

Then, system (2) is transformed into

$$\begin{aligned} x' \Phi &= y, \\ y' \Phi &= g(x) + \varepsilon [f(x, y) + \mu h(x, y)], \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where primes denote the differentiation with respect to φ . Note that system (2) has two unknowns x and y while (5) has three. The basic idea of the NTT method is as follows: we can choose an arbitrary 2π -periodic smooth function for x such that it describes the homoclinic orbit, then the other two unknowns y and Φ can be solved from (5) by the perturbation method, and the value of parameter μ for the homoclinic bifurcation can be determined as well.

We remark that the critical value of μ obtained by the NTT method is independent of the choice of x . Since Φ is 2π -periodic, it is natural to use trigonometric functions for x . For instance, to approximate the homoclinic orbit in (5), we consider the following expression

$$x(\varphi) = p \cos(2\varphi) + q, \quad (6)$$

where p and q are reals to be determined. The homoclinic orbit approaches the equilibrium as $\varphi \rightarrow 0$, $\varphi \rightarrow \pi$ and $\varphi \rightarrow 2\pi$. As φ increases from 0 to π , (6) describes the homoclinic orbit in a clockwise direction. As φ keeps increasing from π to 2π , it describes the orbit again in a reverse direction. We note that $x(\varphi) = x(2\pi - \varphi)$, that is, $x(\varphi)$ is symmetric with respect to the line $\varphi = \pi$. Therefore, it is sufficient to consider system (5) for $\varphi \in [0, \pi]$.

Observe that we prefer to use $\cos(2\varphi)$ instead of $\cos(\varphi)$ in order to avoid the appearance of a square root in the subsequent computation. We explain better the advantages of this choice in the paragraph of Eq. (45).

Next, we apply the perturbation method to approximate the homoclinic orbit. Assume that the analytical solution can be expressed by power series of ε as

$$\begin{aligned} x(\varphi) &= p \cos(2\varphi) + q = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \varepsilon^i x_i(\varphi) \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \varepsilon^i (p_i \cos(2\varphi) + q_i), \\ y(\varphi) &= \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \varepsilon^i y_i(\varphi), \quad \Phi(\varphi) = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \varepsilon^i \Phi_i(\varphi), \quad \mu = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \varepsilon^i \mu_i, \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where p_i , q_i and μ_i are reals, $y_i(\varphi)$ and $\Phi_i(\varphi)$ are 2π -periodic functions in φ .

Substituting (7) into (5), expanding the functions $g(x)$, $f(x, y)$ and $h(x, y)$ in the Taylor series about $\varepsilon = 0$ and equating the coefficients of equal powers of ε lead to the following equations

$$\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^0): x'_0 \Phi_0 = y_0, \quad (8a)$$

$$y'_0 \Phi_0 = g(x_0), \quad (8b)$$

and

$\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^i)(i \in \mathbb{Z}^+)$:

$$\sum_{k=0}^i x'_k \Phi_{i-k} = y_i, \quad (9a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=0}^i y'_k \Phi_{i-k} &= \frac{1}{i!} \frac{d^i g(x)}{d\varepsilon^i} \Big|_{\varepsilon=0} + \frac{1}{(i-1)!} \frac{d^{(i-1)} f(x, y)}{d\varepsilon^{(i-1)}} \Big|_{\varepsilon=0} \\ &+ \sum_{k=0}^{i-1} \mu_{i-k-1} \frac{1}{k!} \frac{d^k h(x, y)}{d\varepsilon^k} \Big|_{\varepsilon=0}. \end{aligned} \quad (9b)$$

2.1 The zero-order solution

First, we need to determine the values of p_0 and q_0 , and to solve y_0 , Φ_0 from the zero-order equation. Considering the fact that the homoclinic orbit approaches the equilibrium as $\varphi \rightarrow 0$, we have

$$g(x_0(0)) = g(p_0 + q_0) = 0. \quad (10)$$

Note that, the unperturbed system of (2) is Hamiltonian with Hamiltonian function

$$H(x, y) = -\frac{1}{2}y^2 + \int_0^x g(u)du.$$

Since the homoclinic orbit concerns the equilibrium

$$(x_0(0), 0) = (p_0 + q_0, 0),$$

the orbit is given by the function

$$H(x_0, y_0) = H(p_0 + q_0, 0), \quad (11)$$

from which y_0 can be solved. From (8a), Φ_0 can be obtained as

$$\Phi_0 = \frac{y_0}{x'_0}. \quad (12)$$

The denominator $x'_0(\varphi)$ vanishes but $x''_0(\varphi) \neq 0$ at $\varphi \in \{0, \frac{\pi}{2}, \pi\}$. Thus, Φ_0 is smooth if, and only if, the numerator $y_0(\varphi)$ also vanishes at the same values of φ . Letting $\varphi = \frac{\pi}{2}$ in (11), we have

$$H(q_0 - p_0, 0) = H(p_0 + q_0, 0), \quad (13)$$

which leads to

$$\int_{p_0+q_0}^{q_0-p_0} g(x)dx = 0. \quad (14)$$

Then, the values of p_0 and q_0 can be determined from (10) and (14). In addition, from (11), we can also derive $y'_0(0) = y'_0(\pi) = 0$ and, consequently, $\Phi_0(0) = \Phi_0(\pi) = 0$.

Note that as was commented on [11, Eq. (18)] the first-order result obtained with the NTT method coincides with the first-order Melnikov function. Therefore, the existence of one locus of homoclinic bifurcations is demonstrated.

2.2 The i th-order ($i \in \mathbb{Z}^+$) solution

Next, we present an algorithm to solve the i th-order solution iteratively. Assume that p_j, q_j, μ_{j-1}, y_j and Φ_j with indices $j = 1, 2, \dots, i-1$ are known and they are obtained from the two equations in $\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^j)$. We also assume that x_j, y_j and Φ_j ($j = 1, 2, \dots, i-1$) are smooth in $[0, \pi]$ and that

$$\begin{aligned} y_j(0) = y_j\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right) = y_j(\pi) = y'_j(0) = y'_j(\pi) \\ = \Phi_j(0) = \Phi_j(\pi) = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Then, we are going to solve p_i, q_i, μ_{i-1}, y_i and Φ_i from (9a)-(9b) and to show that y_i and Φ_i satisfy (15) as well. We want to rewrite the two equations such that the left-hand sides only contain the terms with unknowns. To this end, we expand the terms on the right-hand side of (9b) by the Faà di Bruno's formula [31]. For the first term, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \left. \frac{1}{i!} \frac{d^i g(x)}{d\varepsilon^i} \right|_{\varepsilon=0} &= \frac{1}{i!} \sum_{k=1}^i \left. \frac{d^k g(x)}{dx^k} \right|_{\varepsilon=0} B_{i,k} \left(\left. \frac{dx}{d\varepsilon} \right|_{\varepsilon=0}, \left. \frac{d^2 x}{d\varepsilon^2} \right|_{\varepsilon=0}, \dots, \left. \frac{d^{(i-k+1)} x}{d\varepsilon^{(i-k+1)}} \right|_{\varepsilon=0} \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{i!} \sum_{k=1}^i \frac{d^k g(x_0)}{dx_0^k} B_{i,k}(x_1, 2x_2, \dots, (i-k+1)!x_{i-k+1}) \\ &= \frac{dg(x_0)}{dx_0} x_i + \frac{1}{i!} \sum_{k=2}^i \frac{d^k g(x_0)}{dx_0^k} B_{i,k}(x_1, 2x_2, \dots, (i-k+1)!x_{i-k+1}), \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

where $B_{i,k}$ is the incomplete Bell polynomial. We use the multivariate formula [31] to expand the second term as

$$\left. \frac{d^i f(x, y)}{d\varepsilon^i} \right|_{\varepsilon=0} = \sum_{1 \leq \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 \leq i} \frac{\partial^{(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2)} f(x_0, y_0)}{\partial x_0^{\alpha_1} \partial y_0^{\alpha_2}} \sum_{s=1}^i \sum_{p_{s,i}(\alpha_1, \alpha_2)} i! \prod_{j=1}^s \frac{x_{\beta_j}^{m_j} y_{\beta_j}^{n_j}}{m_j! n_j!}, \quad (17)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} p_{s,i}(\alpha_1, \alpha_2) &= \{(m_1, m_2, \dots, m_s, n_1, n_2, \dots, n_s, \beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_s) : m_j, n_j, \beta_j \in \mathbb{N}, m_j^2 + n_j^2 \neq 0, \\ &0 < \beta_1 < \dots < \beta_s, \sum_{j=1}^s m_j = \alpha_1, \sum_{j=1}^s n_j = \alpha_2 \text{ and } \sum_{j=1}^s (m_j + n_j)\beta_j = i\}. \end{aligned}$$

Analogously, the other terms can also be expanded using the above formula. Then, we can find the terms with unknowns in the expansions, and (9a)-(9b) can be rewritten as

$$x'_0 \Phi_i + x'_i \Phi_0 - y_i = R_{i1}(\varphi), \quad (18a)$$

$$y'_0 \Phi_i + y'_i \Phi_0 - \frac{dg(x_0)}{dx_0} x_i - \mu_{i-1} h(x_0, y_0) = R_{i2}(\varphi), \quad (18b)$$

Eliminating Φ_i between (18a) and (18b), and considering the zero-order equation (8a)-(8b), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} -y'_0 y_i - x'_0 \Phi_0 y'_i + y'_0 \Phi_0 x'_i + \frac{dg(x_0)}{dx_0} x'_0 x_i \\ + \mu_{i-1} x'_0 h(x_0, y_0) \\ = -y'_0 y_i - y_0 y'_i + g(x_0) x'_i + \frac{dg(x_0)}{dx_0} x'_0 x_i \\ + \mu_{i-1} x'_0 h(x_0, y_0) \\ = -[y_0 y_i - g(x_0) x_i]' + \mu_{i-1} x'_0 h(x_0, y_0) \\ = R_{i1} y'_0 - R_{i2} x'_0. \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

Letting $G_i(\varphi) = R_{i1} y'_0 - R_{i2} x'_0$ and integrating (19) with respect to φ leads to

$$\begin{aligned} -y_0 y_i + g(x_0) x_i + \mu_{i-1} \int_0^\varphi x'_0(\tau) h(x_0(\tau), y_0(\tau)) d\tau \\ = \int_0^\varphi G_i(\tau) d\tau. \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

where $R_{i1}(\varphi)$ and $R_{i2}(\varphi)$ represent the remaining terms in the corresponding equation.

Since the homoclinic orbit approaches the equilibrium as $\varphi \rightarrow \pi$, we can obtain two algebraic equations with unknowns p_i , q_i and μ_{i-1} by letting $\varphi = \pi$ in (18b) and (20). In fact, the equation derived from (18b) can also be obtained by letting $\varphi = 0$. Moreover, substituting $\varphi = \frac{\pi}{2}$ into (20) leads to another algebraic equation

with the same unknowns. Then, we have the following system of linear equations

$$\mathbf{A}(p_i, q_i, \mu_{i-1})^T = \mathbf{B}_i, \quad (21)$$

with

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{pmatrix} -\frac{dg(x)}{dx}\Big|_{x=x_0(\pi)} & -\frac{dg(x)}{dx}\Big|_{x=x_0(\pi)} & -h(p_0 + q_0, 0) \\ 0 & 0 & \int_0^\pi x'_0 h(x_0, y_0) d\varphi \\ -g(q_0 - p_0) & g(q_0 - p_0) & \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} x'_0 h(x_0, y_0) d\varphi \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{B}_i = \begin{pmatrix} R_{i2}(\pi) \\ \int_0^\pi G_i(\varphi) d\varphi \\ \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} G_i(\varphi) d\varphi \end{pmatrix}. \quad (22)$$

Proposition 1 System (21) has a unique solution if, and only if, $\int_{\Gamma_0} h(x, y) dx \neq 0$.

Proof System (21) has a unique solution if, and only if,

$$\det(\mathbf{A}) = 2g(q_0 - p_0) \frac{dg(x)}{dx}\Big|_{x=x_0(\pi)} \int_0^\pi x'_0 h(x_0, y_0) d\varphi \neq 0.$$

Note that, $\int_0^\pi x'_0 h(x_0, y_0) d\varphi = \int_{\Gamma_0} h(x, y) dx$ since the zero-order solution describes the unperturbed homoclinic orbit once as φ increases from 0 to π . Thus, proving this proposition is equivalent to showing $g(q_0 - p_0) \neq 0$ and $\frac{dg(x)}{dx}\Big|_{x=x_0(\pi)} \neq 0$.

Obviously, $(x_0(\frac{\pi}{2}), 0) = (q_0 - p_0, 0)$ is not an equilibrium in the unperturbed system of (5) which immediately implies that $g(q_0 - p_0) \neq 0$.

As we have mentioned, the zero-order solution approaches the hyperbolic saddle as $\varphi \rightarrow \pi$. Then, the characteristic polynomial of linearization matrix at the hyperbolic saddle is given by

$$p(\lambda) = \lambda^2 - \frac{dg(x)}{dx}\Big|_{x=x_0(\pi)}. \quad (23)$$

Therefore, we have $\frac{dg(x)}{dx}\Big|_{x=x_0(\pi)} > 0$. \square

Once the unique solution of (21) is determined, y_i and Φ_i can be solved from (20) and (18a), respectively. Since x'_0 and y_0 vanish at $\varphi \in \{0, \frac{\pi}{2}, \pi\}$, it is necessary to show that y_i and Φ_i are smooth at these values. To this end, we introduce the following two propositions.

Proposition 2 The function $y_i(\varphi)$ obtained from (20) is smooth in $[0, \pi]$. Moreover, it vanishes at $\varphi \in \{0, \frac{\pi}{2}, \pi\}$.

Proof From (20), y_i can be expressed as

$$y_i = \frac{g(x_0)x_i + \mu_{i-1} \int_0^\varphi x'_0 h(x_0, y_0) d\varphi - \int_0^\varphi G_i d\varphi}{y_0} \equiv \frac{L(\varphi)}{y_0}. \quad (24)$$

Firstly, we prove this proposition for $\varphi \in \{0, \pi\}$. For the denominator, we have $y_0(\varphi) = 0$, $y'_0(\varphi) = 0$ and $y''_0(\varphi) \neq 0$ at $\varphi \in \{0, \pi\}$. We are going to show that the numerator also vanishes at least with the same multiplicity as the denominator.

Since μ_{i-1} is determined from (21), we have $L(\varphi) = 0$ at $\varphi \in \{0, \pi\}$. The first-order derivative of $L(\varphi)$ is given by

$$L'(\varphi) = \frac{dg(x_0)}{dx_0} x'_0 x_i + g(x_0) x'_i + \mu_{i-1} x'_0 h(x_0, y_0) - R_{i1} y'_0 + R_{i2} x'_0. \quad (25)$$

For $\varphi \in \{0, \pi\}$, $L'(\varphi) = 0$ since $x'_i(\varphi) = 0$ and $y'_0(\varphi) = 0$. Analogously, we can obtain the second-order derivative of $L(\varphi)$ as

$$L''(\varphi) = \frac{d^2 g(x_0)}{dx_0^2} (x'_0)^2 x_i + 2 \frac{dg(x_0)}{dx_0} x'_0 x'_i + g(x_0) x''_i - R'_{i1} y'_0 + R'_{i2} x'_0 + \mu_{i-1} \left[\frac{\partial h(x_0, y_0)}{\partial x_0} (x'_0)^2 + \frac{\partial h(x_0, y_0)}{\partial y_0} y'_0 \right] - R_{i1} y''_0 + x''_0 \left[\frac{dg(x_0)}{dx_0} x_i + \mu_{i-1} h(x_0, y_0) + R_{i2} \right]. \quad (26)$$

According to the definition in (18a), R_{i1} can be written as

$$R_{i1} = - \sum_{k=1}^{i-1} x'_k \Phi_{i-k}, \quad (27)$$

which implies that $R_{i1}(0) = R_{i1}(\pi) = 0$. Moreover, it follows from system (21) that, for $\varphi \in \{0, \pi\}$,

$$\frac{dg(x_0)}{dx_0} x_i + \mu_{i-1} h(x_0, y_0) + R_{i2} = 0. \quad (28)$$

Thus, for $\varphi \in \{0, \pi\}$, we have $L''(\varphi) = 0$, and consequently, $y_i(\varphi) = 0$.

Next, we consider the case $\varphi = \frac{\pi}{2}$. Analogously, we have $y_0\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right) = 0$ and $y'_0\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right) \neq 0$. From (21) and (25), we obtain $L\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right) = L'\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right) = 0$, which leads to $y_i\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right) = 0$.

For $\varphi \in \left\{0, \frac{\pi}{2}, \pi\right\}$, we have shown that y_i is continuous, and it implies that y_i is smooth at these values. \square

Proposition 3 *The function $\Phi_i(\varphi)$ obtained from (18a) is smooth in $[0, \pi]$. Moreover, $\Phi_i(\varphi)$ and $y'_i(\varphi)$ vanish at $\varphi \in \{0, \pi\}$.*

Proof From (18a), $\Phi_i(\varphi)$ can be expressed as

$$\Phi_i(\varphi) = \frac{R_{i1}(\varphi) + y_i(\varphi) - x'_i(\varphi)\Phi_0(\varphi)}{x'_0(\varphi)} \equiv \frac{F(\varphi)}{x'_0(\varphi)}. \quad (29)$$

For the denominator of Φ_i , we have $x'_0(\varphi) = 0$ and $x''_0(\varphi) \neq 0$ at $\varphi \in \left\{0, \frac{\pi}{2}, \pi\right\}$. Applying proposition 2, the numerator $F(\varphi)$ also vanishes at $\varphi \in \left\{0, \frac{\pi}{2}, \pi\right\}$. Thus, Φ_i is continuous at $\varphi \in \left\{0, \frac{\pi}{2}, \pi\right\}$, and it implies that it is smooth at these values.

The computation of derivatives of (18a) and (18b) at $\varphi = 0$ leads to

$$\begin{pmatrix} x''_0(0) & -1 \\ y''_0(0) & \Phi'_0(0) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \Phi_i(0) \\ y'_i(0) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (30)$$

From (8a), we have

$$\begin{aligned} y''_0(0) &= x'''_0(0)\Phi_0(0) + 2x''_0(0)\Phi'_0(0) + x'_0(0)\Phi''_0(0) \\ &= 2x''_0(0)\Phi'_0(0). \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

Thus, the determinant of the 2×2 matrix in (30) is $\frac{3}{2}y''_0(0) \neq 0$. Consequently, (30) has a unique solution given by

$$\Phi_i(0) = y'_i(0) = 0.$$

Analogously, we also have $\Phi_i(\pi) = y'_i(\pi) = 0$. \square

Propositions 2 and 3 show that y_i and Φ_i also satisfy (15). Then, it follows from (7) that

$$y(0) = y(\pi) = \Phi(0) = \Phi(\pi) = 0, \quad (32)$$

which guarantees that the solution obtained by the NTT method approaches the equilibrium as $\varphi \rightarrow 0$ and $\varphi \rightarrow \pi$.

We end this section with a short summary of the important result achieved. First, note that the existence and uniqueness of the homoclinic connection is guaranteed, because the outcome obtained with the NTT method to the first order matches the result given by the Melnikov function [11]. Therefore, we have shown that a parameterization in the phase space of the homoclinic orbit of system (5) (and, equivalently, of system (2)) is expressed in the form (7) if, and only if, $\int_{\Gamma_0} h(x, y) dx \neq 0$, where Γ_0 is the homoclinic orbit in the unperturbed system. In addition, we also get the locus in the parameter space where such a connection exists.

3 Application to the quadratic Takens-Bogdanov normal form

In this section, we apply the method presented in section 2 to the Takens-Bogdanov system (1). Our goal is to find the analytical approximation of the homoclinic bifurcation curve up to any desired order in the parameter space η_1 - η_2 . Simultaneously, an approximation of the homoclinic orbit in the phase plane will be obtained.

To study the homoclinic orbit, we use the following blow-up

$$\begin{aligned} \eta_1 &= -\varepsilon^4, \quad \eta_2 = \nu_2 \varepsilon^2, \\ x &= \varepsilon^2 X, \quad y = \varepsilon^3 Y, \quad t = \varepsilon^{-1} \xi. \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

Then, system (1) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dX}{d\xi} &= Y, \\ \frac{dY}{d\xi} &= -1 + X^2 + \varepsilon(\nu_2 Y + XY). \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

For the sake of convenience, we substitute $(X(\xi), Y(\xi), \xi)$ in (34) with $(x(t), y(t), t)$ and transform the equations into φ domain using the nonlinear time transformation (3). Then, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} x' \Phi &= y, \\ y' \Phi &= -1 + x^2 + \varepsilon(\nu_2 y + xy). \end{aligned} \quad (35)$$

For this system, $g(x) = -1 + x^2$, $f(x, y) = xy$ and $h(x, y) = y$. The unperturbed system possesses a homoclinic orbit Γ_0 to the saddle $(1, 0)$ that surrounds the center $(-1, 0)$. We are going to seek a perturbation solution of the form

$$\begin{aligned} x(\varphi) &= p \cos(2\varphi) + q = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \varepsilon^i x_i(\varphi) \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \varepsilon^i (p_i \cos(2\varphi) + q_i), \\ y(\varphi) &= \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \varepsilon^i y_i(\varphi), \quad \Phi(\varphi) = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \varepsilon^i \Phi_i(\varphi), \quad \nu_2 = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \varepsilon^i \nu_{2i}. \end{aligned} \quad (36)$$

From (10) and (14), we obtain

$$x_0 = \frac{3}{2} \cos 2\varphi - \frac{1}{2}. \quad (37)$$

The homoclinic orbit Γ_0 is given by

$$-\frac{y_0^2}{2} + \frac{1}{3}(x_0 + 2)(x_0 - 1)^2 = 0, \quad -2 \leq x_0 \leq -1. \quad (38)$$

Then, y_0 and Φ_0 can be obtained from (38) and (12) as

$$y_0 = -3\sqrt{2} \cos \varphi \sin^2 \varphi \quad \text{and} \quad \Phi_0 = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} \sin \varphi. \quad (39)$$

Now, we can apply the algorithm introduced in Sect. 2.2 to find iteratively the i th-order solution ($i \in \mathbb{Z}^+$). The matrix \mathbf{A} in system (21) is given by

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{pmatrix} -2 & -2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{24\sqrt{2}}{5} \\ -3 & 3 & \frac{12\sqrt{2}}{5} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (40)$$

Note that, $\int_{\Gamma_0} h(x, y) dx = \frac{24\sqrt{2}}{5} \neq 0$. Then, by Proposition 1, one can obtain a unique solution in each order. We do the computations with Maple and thus it is not necessary to use the expansions (16) and (17) to find R_{i1} and R_{i2} . Therefore, it is very efficient to obtain high-order solution. For instance, up to the 5th-order,

x , y and Φ are given by

$$\begin{aligned} x &= \frac{3}{2} \cos 2\varphi - \frac{1}{2} + (\cos 2\varphi - 1) \left(\frac{9}{196} \varepsilon^2 - \frac{243}{84035} \varepsilon^4 \right), \\ y &= -3\sqrt{2} \cos \varphi \sin^2 \varphi - \frac{18}{7} \varepsilon \cos^2 \varphi \sin^2 \varphi \\ &\quad - \frac{9\sqrt{2}}{196} \varepsilon^2 \cos \varphi \sin^2 \varphi (5 + 9 \cos^2 \varphi) \\ &\quad - \frac{27}{2401} \varepsilon^3 \cos^2 \varphi \sin^2 \varphi (18 - 7 \cos^2 \varphi) \\ &\quad + \frac{81\sqrt{2}}{2689120} \varepsilon^4 \cos \varphi \sin^2 \varphi (445 - 382 \cos^2 \varphi \\ &\quad \quad + 609 \cos^4 \varphi), \\ \Phi &= \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} \sin \varphi + \frac{3}{7} \varepsilon \sin \varphi \cos \varphi \\ &\quad + \frac{9\sqrt{2}}{392} \varepsilon^2 \sin \varphi (1 + 3 \cos^2 \varphi) \\ &\quad + \frac{9}{4802} \varepsilon^3 \sin \varphi \cos \varphi (11 - 7 \cos^2 \varphi) \\ &\quad - \frac{27\sqrt{2}}{5378240} \varepsilon^4 \sin \varphi (393 + 38 \cos^2 \varphi + 609 \cos^4 \varphi). \end{aligned} \quad (41)$$

The first four nonzero terms of ν_2 are given by

$$\nu_2 = \frac{5}{7} + \frac{72}{2401} \varepsilon^2 - \frac{30024}{45294865} \varepsilon^4 - \frac{2352961656}{11108339166925} \varepsilon^6, \quad (42)$$

and it is the same as that obtained in [29, Eq. (13)]. Using the NTT method, we have greatly improved the result. We obtain the solution of ν_2 up to the 21st-order as

$$\begin{aligned}
\nu_2 = & \frac{5}{7} + \frac{72}{2401}\varepsilon^2 - \frac{30024}{45294865}\varepsilon^4 - \frac{2352961656}{11108339166925}\varepsilon^6 + \frac{161066618396136}{2724264638992521625}\varepsilon^8 \\
& - \frac{28575844096870898712}{1622558397660750917241875}\varepsilon^{10} + \frac{37409973403083644863711656}{6764713681983284597882721784375}\varepsilon^{12} \\
& - \frac{1301593321483486009213262204378664}{750205319977359363432143692632890996875}\varepsilon^{14} \\
& + \frac{750633455019308628819042126726886218707352}{1366817906371309055843841557575267655935039046875}\varepsilon^{16} \\
& - \frac{2188961083333347178341822657596953981848275462851032}{12451199287907137102778709466943415347212749443284171484375}\varepsilon^{18} \\
& + \frac{1289326941251660725073133052778275691207040442626311930438856}{22685152569996135996229496037325376035529199986794205676507927734375}\varepsilon^{20} + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^{22}).
\end{aligned} \tag{43}$$

It follows from blow-up (33) that the relation between η_1 and η_2 can be obtained as

$$\begin{aligned}
\eta_1 = & -\frac{49}{25}\eta_2^2 + \frac{144}{625}\eta_2^3 - \frac{345168}{8421875}\eta_2^4 + \frac{7223269392}{1475301953125}\eta_2^5 + \frac{217443738022416}{258436019638671875}\eta_2^6 \\
& - \frac{128238997026174572592}{109945143654781982421875}\eta_2^7 + \frac{247301200098451696690231056}{327413889175349374102783203125}\eta_2^8 \\
& - \frac{53798674401861253415685619677494928}{129679040090055819961716862640380859375}\eta_2^9 \\
& + \frac{36033593800112844122896929791774975483028144}{168761070523124399456865779247390338897705078125}\eta_2^{10} \\
& - \frac{233908194610872498760524641986409170542376041955248}{219621450809111304577508662733006045837276363372802734375}\eta_2^{11} + \mathcal{O}(\eta_2^{12}).
\end{aligned} \tag{44}$$

Remark that the above results are obtained in a standard laptop in a few seconds. To illustrate the validity of the outcome obtained by the NTT method, the analytical results are compared with numerical continuations obtained by AUTO and MatCont [32, 33] in Fig. 2 and 3. They are in good agreement and the higher-order solution improves the accuracy, especially for large parameter values.

We comment now why we use 2φ instead of φ in the expression of $x(\varphi)$ (see Eqs. (6) and (36)). For the quadratic Takens-Bogdanov normal form, if we employ $x(\varphi) = a \cos(\varphi) + b$ to describe the homoclinic orbit, the zero-order solution would become

$$\begin{aligned}
x_0 &= \frac{3}{2} \cos(\varphi) - \frac{1}{2}, \\
y_0 &= \frac{3}{2} \sin(\varphi) \sqrt{1 - \cos(\varphi)}, \\
\Phi_0 &= -\sqrt{1 - \cos(\varphi)}.
\end{aligned} \tag{45}$$

The function Φ_0 obtained is not differentiable at $\varphi = 0$. Furthermore, the occurrence of the square root makes the computation more complicated. Consequently, we choose 2φ instead of φ .

We devote the last part of this section to show the relation between our results and those presented in Ref. [30], where the authors have also studied the normal form of the reduced system on the 2D center manifold near the Takens-Bogdanov bifurcation. They have applied the R-P method and the generalized L-P method with hyperbolic functions to approximate the homoclinic orbit in system [30, Eq. (28)]. This system is equivalent to (34), if we let $a_1 = b_1 = d = e = 0$, $a = \sqrt{2}b$ and apply the following scaling in space variables and time

$$u = 2x, \quad v = 2\sqrt{2}y, \quad \tau = 2\nu_2, \quad s = \frac{t}{\sqrt{2}}. \tag{46}$$

Then, the solution obtained in [30, Sect. 3.2] can be rewritten as

Fig. 2 Comparison between numerical continuation (solid) and analytical approximations (3rd-order: o; 11th-order: star) for the homoclinic bifurcation of (1).

$$\begin{aligned}
x(\xi) &= 1 - 3\operatorname{sech}^2\left(\frac{\xi}{\sqrt{2}}\right) - \varepsilon^2 \frac{9}{98}\operatorname{sech}^2\left(\frac{\xi}{\sqrt{2}}\right) + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^4), \\
y(\xi) &= 3\sqrt{2}\operatorname{sech}^2\left(\frac{\xi}{\sqrt{2}}\right)\tanh\left(\frac{\xi}{\sqrt{2}}\right) \\
&\quad - \varepsilon \frac{18}{7}\operatorname{sech}^2\left(\frac{\xi}{\sqrt{2}}\right)\tanh^2\left(\frac{\xi}{\sqrt{2}}\right) \\
&\quad + \varepsilon^2 \frac{9\sqrt{2}}{196}\operatorname{sech}^2\left(\frac{\xi}{\sqrt{2}}\right)\tanh\left(\frac{\xi}{\sqrt{2}}\right) \\
&\quad \times \left[14 - 9\operatorname{sech}^2\left(\frac{\xi}{\sqrt{2}}\right)\right] + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3), \\
\frac{d\xi}{ds} = \omega(\xi) &= 1 - \varepsilon \frac{3\sqrt{2}}{7}\tanh\left(\frac{\xi}{\sqrt{2}}\right) \\
&\quad + \varepsilon^2 \frac{9}{196}\left[4 - 3\operatorname{sech}^2\left(\frac{\xi}{\sqrt{2}}\right)\right] + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3). \quad (47)
\end{aligned}$$

The following theorem shows that the solutions obtained by the NTT method and the generalized L-P method are equivalent under a one-to-one correspondence.

Theorem 1 *The solution (41) is equivalent to (47) up to order ε^2 under the one-to-one correspondence given by*

$$\sin \varphi = \operatorname{sech}\left(\frac{\xi}{\sqrt{2}}\right), \quad \text{for } \varphi \in (0, \pi) \rightarrow \xi \in (-\infty, \infty). \quad (48)$$

Proof The correspondence (48) leads to

$$\cos^2 \varphi = 1 - \sin^2 \varphi = 1 - \operatorname{sech}^2\left(\frac{\xi}{\sqrt{2}}\right) = \tanh^2\left(\frac{\xi}{\sqrt{2}}\right). \quad (49)$$

Then, for $\varphi \in (0, \pi) \rightarrow \xi \in (-\infty, \infty)$, we have

$$\cos \varphi = -\tanh\left(\frac{\xi}{\sqrt{2}}\right). \quad (50)$$

Substituting (48) and (50) into $x(\xi)$ and $y(\xi)$ in (47), one can obtain $x(\varphi)$ and $y(\varphi)$ in (41) up to order ε^2 . Moreover, $\Phi(\varphi)$ can be obtained as

$$\begin{aligned}
\Phi(\varphi) &= \frac{d\varphi}{ds} = \frac{d\varphi}{d \sin \varphi} \frac{d\left(\operatorname{sech}\left(\frac{\xi}{\sqrt{2}}\right)\right)}{d\xi} \frac{d\xi}{ds} \\
&= \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} \omega(\xi) \sin \varphi.
\end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof. \square

We remark that, in [30], the authors have also shown the solution in $\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3)$. However, the result is not correct. Multiplying both sides of [30, Eq. (45)] by \hat{u}'_0 and integrating both sides from ξ_0 to ξ , the authors obtain [30, Eq. (64)]. We find that the left-hand side of this equation is wrong. Performing the same procedure, we obtain the correct equation as

$$\begin{aligned}
&(\omega_3 \hat{u}'_0{}^2 + \hat{u}'_0 \hat{u}'_3 - \hat{u}_3 \hat{u}'_0{}') \Big|_{\xi_0}^{\xi} \\
&+ \frac{1944}{7a^3} \left(\frac{6}{49} b^3 + bd \right) \frac{\sinh^3(x)}{\cosh^9(x)} \Big|_{\xi_0}^{\xi} \\
&- \frac{432}{49a^3} (6b^3 - 5b^2 a_1 + 21bd) \frac{\sinh^3 x}{\cosh^7(x)} \Big|_{\xi_0}^{\xi} \\
&= \int_{\xi_0}^{\xi} \hat{u}'_0(\text{R.H.S. of [30, Eq. (45)]}) dx. \quad (51)
\end{aligned}$$

Then, applying the procedure of changing the integration variables introduced in [30, sect. 3.2] leads to the

Fig. 3 Comparison between numerical continuations (solid) and analytical approximations (3rd-order: o; 11th-order: star) for the homoclinic orbit of (1) with: (a) $\eta_1 = -1$; (b) $\eta_1 = -5$; (c) $\eta_1 = -10$.

following correct solution to [30, Eq. (28)] up to $\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3)$

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{u}_3 &= 0, \\ \hat{v}_3 &= \frac{36}{49a^3} \left(-20abb_1 + 20a_1b^2 - \frac{66}{49}b^3 - 11bd \right) \\ &\quad \times \operatorname{sech}^2 \xi \tanh^2 \xi \\ &\quad + \frac{12}{7a^3} \left(28ae - 3bd - \frac{18}{49}b^3 \right) \operatorname{sech}^4 \xi \tanh^2 \xi, \\ \omega_3 &= \frac{6}{49a^3} \left(-10abb_1 + 5a_1b^2 - \frac{12}{49}b^3 - 2bd \right) \tanh \xi \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{7a^3} \left(28ae - 3bd - \frac{18}{49}b^3 \right) \operatorname{sech}^2 \xi \tanh \xi. \quad (52) \end{aligned}$$

If we transform the solution (52) to the one for system (1), it is also equivalent to that obtained by the NTT method under the one-to-one correspondence given in theorem 1. Therefore, the solution (41) is equivalent to that in [30] up to order $\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3)$.

Remark that, as opposed to what happens with the L-P method, with our approach we have not a simple representation of the orbit as a function of time. From (3), t and φ are related in the following complicated manner

$$t = \int_{\varphi^*}^{\varphi} \frac{d\theta}{\Phi(\theta)},$$

where $\varphi = \varphi^*$, when $t = 0$. In practical applications, a representation of the orbit as a function of time can be useful, for example, to start a continuation of the homoclinic orbit with AUTO or MatCont. On the other hand, the results presented in this paper correspond to the quadratic Takens-Bogdanov normal form (1). Thus, for applications where it is not enough the truncation to this quadratic normal form, its usefulness may be very limited.

4 Conclusions

In this paper, we have presented an algorithm based on the NTT method to find the analytical approximation of the homoclinic orbits in some autonomous nonlinear oscillators. With the algorithm provided, for the first time in the literature, we are able to obtain a unique perturbation solution up to any desired order. We have also applied this method to the well-known Takens-Bogdanov normal form with quadratic terms. The approximation of the homoclinic orbit has been greatly improved. The analytical results are compared with numerical continuations in both parameter space and phase planes, and they are in good agreement. Using the NTT method, we express the solution in terms of the trigonometric functions. The solutions are equivalent to that obtained with the generalized L-P method using hyperbolic functions. The advantage of the present method is that the trigonometric functions are easier to handle so that it is very efficient to obtain the higher-order solution.

Compliance with ethical standards

Conflict of interest The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of the paper.

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